

NANORIGO

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Proceedings of the NANORIGO Special Scientific Coordination Meeting

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2-3 February 2023

Rudolf Reuther and Lesley Tobin
Environmental Assessments (ENAS)

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Foreword

These proceedings are a record of the final NANORIGO Special Scientific Coordination Meeting (SSCM) that took place on 2-3 February 2023 at Burg Windeck, Germany.

They provide a collection of the presentations given by various project partners and a summary of the reflections and discussions that followed during the different sessions with a focus on specific topics still to be addressed at the end of the NANORIGO project (see [Appendix 2. Meeting Agenda](#)).

Purpose of the NANORIGO SSCM

The idea of this SSCM was to reflect again on some fundamental questions and critical and cross-cutting issues that have come up during the NANORIGO project. But also, to discuss best ways forward on how to optimize and maximize the impact of the project's main outcomes considering the newly changing regulatory and political landscape.

Another purpose was to discuss and support the finalization of some relevant pending deliverables.

This meeting provided a final opportunity for project partners to meet again in person, something that was not possible during most of the project's duration due to the pandemic, and to identify and share lessons learnt for future activities.

Structure and procedure of the SSCM

The SSCM was structured into various thematic sessions and designed to allow an open discussion among all participants and across the most essential topics (see [Appendix 2. Meeting Agenda](#)).

Before the meeting, a questionnaire was prepared and distributed in advance to all participants to obtain their responses and statements on specific and fundamental issues that had not been sufficiently addressed during the four years of NANORIGO (see [Appendix 4. Questionnaire](#) and [Appendix 5. Summary of Responses to Questionnaire](#)). The responses to this questionnaire served as a starting point and springboard for the many discussions and debates that took place during the meeting. While Session 1 focused on what had been achieved, with a reflection on main outcomes of the final NMBP-13 stakeholder conference at the OECD, Session 2 provided ample space for an open discussion of the most critical issues that emerged and were addressed over the four years of the project. As some relevant deliverables were pending, Session 3 was devoted to bringing together ideas and suggestion on how to optimize/maximize and operationalize their final impact. In Session 4, participants once again reflected on the previous discussions and on lessons learned, while Session 5 allowed participants to look back over four years of intense collaborative and transdisciplinary work with an eye on the future, while identifying and describing the most inspiring moments that they experienced.

Session 1: Synopsis and discussion of what we have achieved in NANORIGO

After a short welcome and introduction to the purpose of the meeting by Rudolf Reuther, the NANORIGO scientific coordinator (see [Appendix 3. Welcome and Introduction to the SSCM](#)), Session 1 was opened by Mark Morrison (OPTIMAT), with a brief overview of, and feedback from, the NMBP-13 stakeholder conference at the OECD in Paris, which took place the week before (24-25 January 2023), re-emphasizing the potential of the three NMBP-13 projects ([Gov4Nano](#), [RiskGone](#) and [NANORIGO](#)) to support the new EU policies and associated initiatives around the EU Green Deal, in

particular the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS), and the PARC and AMI2030 initiatives, all of which strongly focus on creating a safe and sustainable environment for chemicals and advanced materials in Europe (see [Appendix 6. Feedback from the OECD Event, Paris](#)). Although the need for a formal organization (e.g., in the form of a 'House' or 'Round Table') was recognized by all conference participants as a means with which to engage regulators, the question remained: Who will guarantee the necessary funding of such a new organization?

One of the key conclusions of the subsequent plenary discussion was that we had reached out mainly to policy makers/regulators and researchers and less to industries and civil societies. Also, that governance is very much about being responsible and making compromises and strategic decisions. It was felt that we became too technical too quickly, and we never fully understood who our target group was. Were we too ambitious and acting on too high a level? Or were we too naïve? It was also agreed that there was too little participation from a wider range of stakeholders from social science fields, e.g., anthropologists, social scientists, and political scientists. Nano is now part of advanced materials and of the wider spectrum of EU political priorities that includes digitalization to enable policy and industry to stand against/compete with other regions. Within NANORIGO we lacked a clear long-term strategy from the Commission that considers and responds to changes in policy priorities. The 'House' as a new organizational form is now pushing against a locked door unless perhaps integrated, e.g., with AMI2030.

The second part of Session 1 was devoted to participants' opinions on the question, "What are the most important results of the NANORIGO project?" To support the discussion, an overview of the main achievements (in terms of achieved deliverables) was first given (see [Appendix 7. What we have achieved in NANORIGO in the last four years](#)). One broadly shared statement was that there were many lessons learnt about implementing such a complex and challenging project, and that we obtained a more holistic and balanced view on the complexity and transdisciplinary nature of risk when it comes to nano- and advanced materials. Also, that risk governance is not a top-down but rather a bottom-up and inclusive approach, encompassing all concerned stakeholders. It was also recognized that there must be expert support for the users to use the data, tools, and the risk governance framework (RGF). It was further emphasized that there is a growing awareness of the need for interdisciplinary actions and that NANORIGO is one of the first projects that has put this awareness into practice. If there is high uncertainty, there is a requirement for guidance through governance and interdisciplinary work. Furthermore, aligning this with the precautionary principle is essential. Yet, the cooperation between the three complex projects may have been more of a hindrance than a bridge to effectively implementing and achieving what had been planned and to adequately respond to external changes: it may have been more effective for the three projects to work independently and in parallel with each other. In the end, the project created an awareness that there are different aspects and different stakeholders with different needs and interests to be considered and balanced. However, it was concluded that data FAIRness (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) was one of the most interesting outcomes, and the Knowledge Readiness Level (KaRL) approach one of the most promising tools.

Session 2: Open discussion of critical issues and questions

Session 2 opened with a short overview/synthesis of the responses to the questionnaire, followed by a discussion of the statements provided (see [Appendix 8. Additional statements](#)). These statements were discussed in the form of a "House of Commons" debate, whereby the participants were divided into two groups according to whether they agreed or disagreed with the statement. The respective

groups lined up facing each other and the debate ensued. As opinions changed during the debate, members could then ‘cross the floor’ accordingly.

To kick off the debate, participants considered the issue that we were midway through the project when it was suddenly decided that there is no need for a Risk Governance Council (RGC). However, without an RGC, there was no entity to host, curate, support or provide access to the use of the established Risk Governance Framework (RGF), the tools and the data. The debate opened with the statement that ‘Industries are not interested if they cannot make a profit’. The ensuing discussion examined the balance of risk vs growth and competitiveness, and that if there isn’t an obvious risk, then growth and competitiveness will prevail. Moreover, if the same institution, e.g., the EU is funding and supporting growth, then growth will outweigh risk governance. If it is agreed that risk governance should be aligned with growth, there must be also an ownership of this risk. Conversely, large industries are often willing to significantly invest to avoid litigation. It was also felt that it was naïve to believe that risk can be measured, and that it should be the subject and result of discussion and compromise and a matter of common agreement and values. The instances of asbestos, lead, tobacco, and others were referred to. In contrast, industry tries to nurture the doubt about the results of a public debate so that RG is unable to enact effective decisions. The case of Exxon was raised, with the view that it was difficult to say that they should have known what they were doing, and that Exxon should be penalized, fined etc., as this shouldn’t automatically dictate all other cases: in such cases, it can be demonstrated that a chemical or material is hazardous or not with equal strength. The real governance lies in finding a balance: it’s not about setting a rule but establishing a rule and being flexible. Nevertheless, it was also agreed that with regulation comes competitive advantage.

The outcome of this session was that even with a UK House of Commons debate, after 10 minutes the participants were largely ‘on the fence’ between the opposing statements. Regulations are for all our benefits, but growth and competitiveness need to be socially responsible.

Following this, the question of the sustainability of the established NANORIGO Risk Governance Framework (RGF) was discussed, and it was agreed that without an active Organizational Form (OF) or Council, the RGF will be doomed to fail. Unfortunately, there is no mandate for such an OF, but an independent, neutral, and trustworthy body is needed that can facilitate a social discourse among all stakeholders.

Session 3: Maximizing and operationalizing impact

Session 3 focused on finalizing pending deliverables and examining how to maximize and operationalize their impact.

D1.9 Integrative perspective on user/stakeholder needs.

This session started with a short introduction on D1.9 Integrative perspective on user/stakeholder needs (and D4.10 Report on multidisciplinary and multistakeholder dialogue) by Daan Schuurbiens (DPF) (see [Appendix 9. D1.9 Stakeholder needs and interests](#)), whereby we addressed the question: “What have we learned from engaging stakeholders into the risk governance process?” It was acknowledged that the issue is demanding and complex, especially when taking into account the fact that needs are diverse and contingent on the type of stakeholder. One view was that in most cases there is too little information to answer the questions raised, but that the RGF could provide support when there is no information. On the other hand, stakeholders do not know what information or

data is relevant for them. Thus, the first step is to formulate the question or the problem. However, issues may arise when the cause of the problem is the lack of information. For this reason, a pre-assessment or framing step is needed, as suggested by the RGF.

Other points were also acknowledged: for example, we often assess the risk of pristine materials, but not of unpredictable conglomerations or of those further down the value chain. Regarding stakeholders' needs, an assessment was performed when developing the Risk Communication Platform and therefore included in D1.9. It was recognized that in the many webinars NANORIGO organized, stakeholders mainly endorsed the idea of a 'House', except for industry, which appeared neither for nor against it. However, the function of the 'House' was not agreed on. What was conclusive was that there is a need for better access to transparent information, since much of it is kept confidential and people 'sit on' reports. Finally, it was pointed out that one stakeholder may have needs that conflict with another, and so it is essential to strike a balance between the different stakeholders' interests and perspectives.

The Risk Communication Platform (contributing to D3.2 and D3.3)

Participants then examined D3.2 (Background document for NANORIGO Nanotechnology Risk Governance Framework (NRGF) (D3.2-A); The Risk Governance Framework prototype demonstrator (D3.2-B); Working document for the NRGF web-platform manual (D3.2-C) and D3.3 (Science-based transdisciplinary Risk Governance Framework (RGF) for manufactured nanomaterials) addressing the Risk Communication Platform as presented by Dana Kühnel (UFZ), based on a 'Blueprint on how to build a risk communication platform to support nano risk governance' (see [Appendix 10. Blueprint: How to build a risk communication platform to support NRG](#)).

The document describes the three pillars of Risk Communication (RC) and provides a review of a stakeholder needs evaluation complemented with a table listing experts or personnel needed to run the RC platform (there is no deliverable directly associated with task T3.5). The question was asked whether RC and communication are the same or two different things? Both have much to do with understandability, and there are overlaps with science communication, a component of which is RC. As part of an outreach activity, a table was prepared with links to other communication platforms. All case studies showed that guidance and expertise is needed to run and interpret the NANORIGO RGF, the executing web platform and its output. Participants also examined the question of whether communication is just information. As in the case of Covid-19: how do we explain to the wider audience which risks are real? In this context, the role of a moderator was deemed to be significant for guiding different stakeholders along the risk governance process, and it was discussed whether the new OF could assume such a role. Users that followed the RC process were unclear about the additional benefits and why they should use this platform. It was therefore emphasized that effective communication of the required information is essential as there is a plethora of sources of misunderstandings and misinterpretations. When civil societies are speaking in different languages, this can lead to different and erroneous interpretations and miscommunication of information to others in ways that are unhelpful or unintelligible. What then? It should be made clear in the RC the difference between risk communication and science communication, depending on the knowledge, background and expertise of the stakeholders. It may also be the case that at times no additional experts are needed. Another question discussed was why someone should pursue RC practices? One reason is that it is an essential step to understand the RG process. It was finally agreed that the RC platform offers guidance and support for that process whenever stakeholders need this for nano-related issues, and beyond. We can show what we mean by communication, which can be an effective tool for showing how to use and benefit from the RGF. In this way, communication is not just about information sharing.

D3.4 Guidance document for RGF

The next deliverable to be discussed was D3.4 Guidance document for RGF, presented by Rudolf Reuther (ENAS) (on behalf of Milja Koponen, FIOH). One of the main questions linked to this deliverable was, “How can we improve and increase the usefulness of this guidance document in the light of the need of end-users that need not only technical assistance along the RG process, and what can it encompass and what not (scope and limitations), as reflected in the various case studies.” It was agreed that this document should not repeat in detail the description of all the tools and resources developed, but rather consistently guide any user through the risk governance process, as provided by the RGF, with corresponding links to the sources of the given information (such as concerned deliverables, technical documents, videos, or publications) (see [Appendix 11. D3.4 Guidance document for RGF - Rudolf Reuther \(ENAS\) on behalf of Milja Koponen \(TTL\)](#))

D5.9 Publication on economic benefits from implementing the RGF based on case studies

D5.9 Publication on economic benefits from implementing the RGF, based on case studies was presented by Martin Mullins (TGO) and discussed intensely among participants (see [Appendix 12. Publication on economic benefits from implementing the RGF, based on case studies](#)). The intention was to have a beta draft by mid-February and then publish as a ~3,000-word paper. However, what was still missing was the economic perspective. As regards economics, the literature shows that improved governance leads to improved economic results. Risk management depends on reliable information and there is a substantial body of knowledge supporting this. Insurance is also part of this and depends on reliable information. Better information means a lower insurance premium. Martin Mullins referenced a 2015 paper that stressed the mutability of risk, and how perceptions alter. We can create a framework, but it must be responsive to change and different taxonomies. He then broached the questions: ‘What is specific about the NANORIGO approach?’ and ‘Are we doing anything different?’ He indicated that we have added value to data readiness, and socio-economic elements, and we have collected and reflected on tools. However, NANORIGO is a mixture of realist and constructivist approaches, and so is economics, and it is tied to future profits. Linking this to D5.9, he said that it will focus on the data we produce and the data readiness, and it will use tools from the financial sector (value and robustness of data) and metricize the quality of the data. It could then have a positive feed into the Risk Governance system. With good data quality and robust methodology, it is possible to make this work. The deliverable will have an academic approach and will suggest and signpost a way forward. This will be exemplified in D5.9 by TiO₂, which has recently been re-classified by ECHA. The RGF will be applied to show how it will work when using these tools.

At the same time, the co-creational approach as used in NANORIGO will be tested aside from regulation and assume a more perceptual approach. RG is data dependent, and it is therefore necessary to look at the quality of the data used as a signpost towards a judicial statement and to broaden it out to a wider stakeholder group.

The next question to be addressed was whether corporate governance is different from other types of governance or if governance is just governance? It was agreed that RG is an umbrella term and a way of widening technocratic corporate governance. It puts pressure on corporations to widen their stakeholder base. Currently, however, it is not bottom-up communication but top-down regulation that almost rules alone and this should change.

The session concluded that the planned 5,000-word paper will be an interdisciplinary and high theory paper that will bring on the debate, and that the SSCM had facilitated a higher quality of

debate than had previously been experienced in NANORIGO. The paper will be about data readiness rather than exposure and hazard. But data may be ready or not, and perceptions of what is 'ready' may differ, too. Finally, it will shine an economic torch on the RGF also to make it more tangible.

D7.5 Options for the form and funding of an NRG Organizational Form

Finally, D7.5 Options for the form and funding of a Nanotechnology Risk Governance Organizational Form, was presented by Mark Morrison (OPTIMAT) and discussed with the audience (see [Appendix 13. Options for the form and funding of an NRG Organizational Form](#)). The discussion started with the question, What has changed since the kick-off? What are the options, the landscape, stakeholder feedback, and operational considerations? A PESTLE analysis will be included in the deliverable, and the subjects of this analysis were presented. These included a description of the different manifestations of the House/Roundtable/OF, the landscape, and the emerging organizations in which the "House" would/could operate, with a summary of the stakeholder consultations and an overview of operational considerations. Here it was emphasized that there are obvious connections between Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) and what we found and what the EC is not addressing yet, that is, the broader societal considerations. We have established the guidance to help their search and this is a real opportunity. There was perhaps concern that the OF would distract from ECHA and EUON. For that reason, the deliverable demonstrates that we have considered the full landscape and that the route through and alignment with AMI2030 is the most promising way to go to achieve legitimacy.

D5.8 Multimedia presentation on results of case studies

Session 3 was finalized by D5.8 Multimedia presentation on results of case studies, with a video presentation of the NANORIGO case studies, including the rubber tyre study, produced and shown by Martin Himly, Sabine Hofer, and Norbert Hofstätter (PLUS). The videos are currently being finalised and will be made available here: <https://zenodo.org/communities/nanoriskgovernance> by June 2023

Session 4: On second thoughts ...

Session 4 provided a discussion platform for "Second thoughts ... and reflection on yesterday and discussion of lessons learned". After a short welcome and brief overview of the previous day's discussion, Rudolf Reuther invited all participants to share their thoughts on lessons learned (see [Appendix 14. Session 4 'On Second Thoughts' - Rudolf Reuther \(ENAS\)](#)). In a roundtable type discussion, feedback and conclusions were exchanged about how partners experienced their work, the results they achieved, and the collaborations not only within NANORIGO but also across the three projects in the NMBP-13 cluster. One of the main topics of discussion was the NANORIGO web-portal, which could be form part of a joint NMBP-13 platform for tools and data that current and future SSbD-focused projects may use, curate, and sustain after the end of the project. It was unanimously agreed that the portal must be curated if it is to exist in the future.

So far, it is not immediately apparent what users can gain from the portal, the subject of intense discussion within the NMBP-13 portal core group. A common agreement has not been reached on the joint use of the portal and how to sustain it, due to a lack of funding to support hosting and regular updating. Although a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) was signed by all three NMBP-13 projects, the way forward is blocked by the absence of funding and curation personnel. Moreover, there will not be a Council or Organizational Form / House / Round Table to maintain it. One option may be to identify people or organizations who are part of the portal core group and

partners in one of the current SSbD projects, and who are willing and able to assume responsibility for and run the portal, as seen with eNanoMapper. In this way, responsibility for the portal should be assumed by an appropriate project or project partner within the EU NanoSafety Cluster (NSC) which could guarantee continuity, in the same way that Idea consult took on eNanoMapper after the end of the project. However, it may be the case that the benefits of the portal are still not so apparent to potential users. Another suggestion was to look at other research data platforms where there is funding from national governments and agencies and learn from these models. There may also be an NSC working group willing to identify a sustainable solution for the NMBP-13 joint portal. This question of continuation of the portal could be also discussed at the forthcoming NSC Venice training school (15–19 May 2023).

It was finally agreed to approach both the SSbD projects, as well as the PARC research partnership to see who is willing to engage. It was also suggested that the micro and nanoplastics CUSP Cluster (www.cusp-research.eu) be approached. However, it was argued that the plastics projects are still at too early a stage to engage. Moreover, due to the great diversity of activities, it may be difficult to obtain an agreement on this, as shown by the previous reluctance of some cluster members to join the eNanoMapper database. It was finally agreed to find a place for the portal within the NSC.

Looking back at the Paris OECD meeting and on the discussions the previous day, it was felt that we are not at the end but in the middle of a dynamic development. For this reason, it is important that we adopt an international, global approach, involve USA entities, industry, and those companies that produce nanomaterials and have the resources to support future efforts.

Originally, NANORIGO was designed to create an umbrella that manifested as a framework encompassing all the interests, needs and the diverse range of stakeholder groups, while at the same time developing a risk governance process that can be applied across different industrial and regulatory sectors. Although the nano risk debate may hamper the development of advanced materials and subsequent innovations, there is a need for a neutral and independent organization that can moderate and coordinate a dialogue to arrive at a solution that everyone can agree on and comply with. But as ultimately there was no concrete mandate, it is difficult to operationalize the governance process that we developed or maintain it beyond the lifespan of the project. The established framework is an open and transparent one with a focus on newly emerging materials, and this was one of the main focal points of NANORIGO. But there needs to be an economic rationale. Who wins and who loses by using the RGF, the tools, and the portal when such an enormous sum of money is involved in large contracts? Who benefits when you drop the portal into the regulatory ecosystem? Companies often pay a lot of money to get a quick fix for their regulatory needs but would not the portal for this purpose. It could be useful in classrooms and universities, but EU authorities may not use it.

In this context, it was stated that the portal is not a commercial tool, but policymakers can use it together with stakeholders to arrive at and form balanced decisions and judgements. The portal is also a route to experts, like a 'shop door'. And again, there are the questions, 'Where is the risk?', 'Who gets ill from exposure?' and 'Can we prove it by using the RGF?' As reporting requirements are at the forefront when new products, substances and materials are developed, the RGF could be useful for this as part of the authorization process. Regulators may ask how we can measure risk, and the portal could assist and serve this purpose in a transparent and inclusive way. One thought-provoking statement, made by Daan Schuurbijs, was that "We all agreed that we may feel bad on the one hand that our outcomes aren't what we wanted. But there has been a lot of mutual learning on the other hand. And we've been learning each other's "languages". So, one conclusion is that we

have achieved a lot despite not having the “shiny” products”. Yet, we still haven’t identified the many problem owners, who don’t have a voice in this play. We have developed a social process and shifted signposts while trying to find solutions to a problem (i.e., a more holistic governance of risks). This is why one lesson that we have learned is to be more aware of what is happening outside a project, especially regarding new material developments and policy initiatives. Better communication with the European Commission and across the three projects would have allowed us to respond earlier and adapt to the new upcoming EU strategies and, where necessary, change our direction accordingly. Having three projects in parallel with rather different directions and priorities was the wrong instrument for the EC and made it more difficult to navigate through the constantly changing institutional and regulatory landscape.

Moreover, there were clear signs from the regulators in the established User Committee group that they were not waiting for a new Council, and it was agreed that we were effective in taking this into account. There remains hope that we can overcome the current fragmentation of the different regulatory fields dealing with chemicals, substances, products, and materials from various industrial and private consumption sectors. Although we could not effectively change the present situation, we at least opened a perspective for the future. We could not materialize the original idea to create an overarching and independent risk governance body that could help stakeholders to communicate and balance any conflicting needs and interests. But the idea of a multi-disciplinary and multi-stakeholder focused risk governance for nanomaterials and chemicals will persist and may get another opportunity to manifest in the future.

Session 5: Looking back on four years of NANORIGO.

In the final session, all participants were asked to reflect on four years of NANORIGO with an eye on the future, and to describe the most inspiring moments they had experienced. One piece of feedback was that we should approach this type of problem (governance of complex, uncertain, and ambiguous risk) less naïvely in the future and just start with the question: ‘Where are the gaps?’. Another comment reflected on the fact that there has been always a broad discussion about how to handle exposure, hazard, and risk of chemicals (and emerging materials), and while what we achieved was inspiring, we should be critical in terms of finding a new and broadly acceptable way to operationalize this. Another eyeopener was how we tried to establish a common agreement (especially with NGOs) on the level of pollution that we can accept, and whether this is indeed achievable.

Further reflection revealed that that the cooperation between the three NMBP-13 projects was ultimately successful, despite numerous hurdles. Moreover, it was inspiring to experience the work achieved in the different case studies to test the tools, the RGF, and the processes under real conditions. In this context, the TiO₂ case study was considered as a real “success story” that helped to identify where the problem (gaps, shortcomings etc.) lies within REACH and CLP, as well as mobilizing numerous stakeholders. The realization of the power held by institutions was a significant moment of insight and it all concurred that that transparency was paramount, although initiating and promoting bilateral communication and dialogue among stakeholders could be challenging. Another revelation was how different stakeholder and interest groups can learn from each other along the governance process and share one another’s views on needs and problems by simply committing to a mutually balanced dialogue and debate culture that can lead to a more trusted environment and a holistic and differentiated understanding of risk. The perspective on how natural and social scientists can learn and benefit from each other through open and transparent

communication and co-creational approaches was highly motivating and encouraging. Through this, the actors can appreciate how much they still have to learn and understand.

All in all, it was perceived that while at the beginning of the project we were rather optimistic about achieving the desired results, in the end, and especially after so many ideas were taken up by new EU initiatives, the idea of an “umbrella” remained an unachievable goal. Nevertheless, it was the inclusiveness and multidisciplinary nature of the approach we developed that created a real added value. At the same time, we realized that there was a power play between the three NMBP-13 projects that had to be accommodated - the joint User Committee became a part of this and an indicator of how the projects would pan out. Ultimately all participants expressed how in one way or another the four years have provided a tremendous learning process in relation to our preconceived ideas of what we thought we knew and understood, and the experience enabled us to perceive complexity more clearly and find solutions by increasing both our sensitivity and awareness of the complex reality we frequently face when assessing unknown risks.

One conclusion drawn was that we need to think in a holistic way as everything has inherent risks and benefits, and this is why risk governance should be underpinned by timely assessment and a pre-cautionary approach as well as a strategy that is both inclusive and sustainable. When we started NANORIGO, we had a snapshot of the situation we faced at that time and we could not take this as a constant but needed to adapt and respond to a continually changing environment. This experience made us more sensitive and aware: something which became an integral part of the process. When we now progress to new projects and initiatives, we can bring with us and apply our latest understanding of the complexity of the world that we are living in. It may not be easy to arrive at the optimal solutions as conditions change, and this is why we must learn to be more adaptive and proactive when we step into the future.

Appendices

Appendix 1. Participants at the SSCM

Name	Organisation
Rudolf Reuther	ENAS
Pieter van Broekhuizen	BKLB
Lesley Tobin	ENAS
Kees Le Blansch	BKLB
Drobne Damjana	UL
Sabine Hofer	PLUS
Norbert Hofstätter	PLUS
Isabel Rodriguez-Llopis	GAIKER
Daan Schuurbijs	DPF
Martin Himly	PLUS
Suman Pokhrel	UniHB
Mark Morrison	OPTIMAT
Ludger Benighaus	DIALOGIK
Dana Kühnel	UFZ
José Santos	SPI
Andreas Hermann	OEKO
Martin Mullins	TGO
Blanca Pozuelo Rollon	ITENE

Appendix 2. Meeting Agenda

Special Scientific Coordination Meeting Agenda	
Meeting Information	
Title:	NANORIGO Special Scientific Coordination Meeting
Date/time:	Wednesday 1 st February – Arrivals; Thursday 2 nd – Friday 3 rd February
Location:	Burg Windeck - Hotel und Restaurant, Kappelwindeckstraße 104, 77815 Bühl/Baden, Deutschland
Contact details:	+49 7223 94 92-0 kontakt@burg-windeck.de
Agenda	
Wednesday 1st February	
19:30	Informal gathering
Thursday 2nd February	
	MODERATORS
08:30-08:50	Arrive at the venue. Tea and Coffee.
08:50-09:00	Welcome Rudolf Reuther (ENAS)
09:00-10:00	Session 1: Synopsis and discussion of what we have achieved in NANORIGO during the last 4 years a) Feedback from the OECD event: conclusions and discussion Mark Morrison (OPTIMAT) [~15 minutes] b) Tour de table – participants' opinions "What are the most important results of the NANORIGO project [content and results]" [~45 minutes] Rudolf Reuther (ENAS)
10:00-12:00 including a coffee/tea break	Session 2: Open discussion of critical issues and questions (based on the questionnaire and statements) Kees Le Blansch and Pieter van Broekhuizen (KLB) Rudolf Reuther will start the discussion with a short overview/synthesis of responses to the questionnaire, followed by a discussion about the statements.
12:00-13:30	Lunch
13:30-15:00	Session 3: Maximising (and operationalising) impact(s) Discussion on finalizing pending deliverables (30 minutes max per deliverable), in particular: D1.9 Integrative prospective on user/stakeholder needs (+ D4.10 Report on multidisciplinary and multistakeholder dialogue) Daan Schuurbiens (DPF) D3.2 and D3.3 Risk Communication Platform Dana Kuehnel (UFZ) D3.4 Guidance document for RGF Rudolf Reuther on behalf of Miija Koponen (TTL) D5.8 Multimedia presentation on results of case studies Martin Himly / Sabine Hofer / Norbert Hofstaetter (PLUS) D5.9 Publication on economic benefits from implementing the RGF, based on case studies. Martin Mullins (TGO) D7.5 Options for the form and funding of a Nanotechnology Risk Governance Organisational Form Mark Morrison (OPTIMAT) Mini-sessions of each 30 minutes (max)
15:00-15:30	Coffee break
15:30-17:30	Session 3: Continued discussion: Maximising (and operationalising) impact(s) Mark Morrison (OPTIMAT), Daan Schuurbiens (DPF)
19:00-22:00	Welcome dinner at Burg Windeck Hotel and Restaurant
Friday 3rd February	
	MODERATORS
09:00-10:30	Session 4: On second thoughts ... Reflection on yesterday and discussion of lessons learned Rudolf Reuther (ENAS) Pieter van Broekhuizen (KLB)
10:30-11:00	Coffee break
11:00-12:00	Session 5: Looking back on 4 years of NANORIGO (with an eye on the future) Inventory of most inspiring moments Rudolf Reuther and all participants
12:00-13:00	Light refreshments
Close	

Appendix 3. Welcome and Introduction to the SSCM - Rudolf Reuther (ENAS)

Welcome and introduction to the SSCM

- ✦ Critically reflect on the **work** we have done, **results** achieved and **impact** expected
- ✦ Look at some of the most critical questions and issues that remain
- ✦ Discuss finalization of deliverables D1.9+4.10, D3.2+3.3, D3.4, D5.8, D5.9, D7.5
- ✦ Debate on where we succeeded well and what we could have made better
- ✦ Discuss how we can maximize/optimize the impact of what we have achieved
- ✦ Looking beyond the project

This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant agreement 825588.

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Appendix 4. Questionnaire - Pieter van Broekhuizen (BKLb), Rudolf Reuther (ENAS), Lesley Tobin (ENAS)

NANORIGO

Section 1 of 3

Reflection on NANORIGO 2019 – 2022

Achievements and Future Use

✕ ⋮

Our meeting will reflect on what we achieved in the four years of NANORIGO (NR) and NMBP-13 joint activities; on what we did not achieve, but hoped to achieve; and on how we organized our efforts within our NANORIGO project, and together with our partner projects Gov4Nano and RiskGONE. At the same time, we will reflect on how our nano risk governance output may, or should, contribute to the EU chemicals strategy for sustainability as one of the pillars of the Green Deal.

To prepare for this Special Scientific Coordination Meeting (SSCM), we are asking all participants to come forward with three topics or statements that you would like to discuss, in addition to the statements/questions provided in questionnaire (see question 13). We ask you to fill in this questionnaire concisely and clearly. Please fill in your own ideas, not necessarily the answer of your institution. We hope your thorough reflection will stimulate active participation in the discussion in the SCCM.

The questions are grouped into two sections concerning: 1) the content and achievements of our work; and 2) questions on the desired (potential) impact and internal project communication and organization.

We ask all participants to fill in this questionnaire before **1st December 2022**.

From your responses/statements, we will formulate and select the topics and priorities for our discussion at the SCCM, and use these for structuring the agenda. The meeting will use different work forms.

Email *

Valid email

Section 2 of 3

About (nano) risk governance > < ⋮

Description (optional)

1. After all we have achieved and learnt within NR, what in fact is your opinion on what Risk Governance should be? Is it simply using risk assessment to control the risks, and is the inclusion of concern assessment self-evident?

Long answer text

2. "RG is more a political process than a scientific process." To what extent do you agree with this statement and why?

Long answer text

3. About the Nano Risk Governance Framework:

In what way should a nano RGF differ essentially from a chemicals RGF?

What would make it nano- specific?

Long answer text

4. Do we really need a special nano RGF besides the more general RGF - and if so/not, why? Or do we only need a **NRGF** specifically for smart (nano) materials (i.e., self-replicating, self-improving systems, etc.)?

Long answer text

5. The aim of a full governance process, including risk assessment as well as concern assessment, elaborated in a deliberative process, should lead to an agreement about a risk management approach. Possibly, not all topics need a full governance approach. Should topics that need a full governance approach be prioritised? And what topics and stakeholders should be involved in this type of prioritising process (if needed)?

Long answer text

6. **Who** (what stakeholder or target group) should be held responsible for initiating a (nano) RG process?

And should these end-users also be responsible for involving all other relevant stakeholders (-representatives) in this process?

Long answer text

7. **What** do you expect from the future use of our NRGF and organisational form (OF)?

Should it be used as such by industry, regulators or CSOs?

Should it be used within specific regulations and risk situations? And what would this look like?

Long answer text

Section 3 of 3

About the work we did in NMBP13/NANORIGO X ⋮

Description (optional)

8. Were matters of principle (issues requiring a strategic choice) related to the risk governance of nanomaterials sufficiently considered and discussed in NANORIGO? If so, why was our attention to concern assessment questions so limited? *

Long answer text

9. Referring back to question 2, 'Is building/optimising a NanoRGF a scientific process or more of a political process?', would it have been better if we'd had a more explicit focus on **how** to organise the governance process, i.e., how could the difficulties/complexities of an inclusive risk governance process be further clarified and how could we advise on this for practical use? *

Long answer text

10. Could the lack of discussions within the NANORIGO team on fundamental and strategic issues related to nano risk governance and the European chemicals policy be a reason why we are ending the project with uncertainties and confusion about the usefulness of the obtained results? *

Long answer text

10. Could the lack of discussions within the NANORIGO team on fundamental and strategic issues related to nano risk governance and the European chemicals policy be a reason why we are ending the project with uncertainties and confusion about the usefulness of the obtained results? *

Long answer text

11. Visibility of our work: What are your thoughts about the peer-reviewed publications throughout the project (as published on the NANORIGO website)? *

- Their strategic importance and relation to (nano) risk governance (during and after the project)?
- Do the publications reflect the key issues we were supposed to address in NANORIGO and as planned in the DOA?
- What is their relevance for the work we did in NANORIGO/NMBP-13?

Long answer text

12. What main lessons did we learn through our work in NANORIGO and NMBP-13? *

Long answer text

13. Please suggest here up to THREE ADDITIONAL specific topics or statements that you would like to discuss during our meeting *

Long answer text

Appendix 5. Summary of Responses to Questionnaire - Rudolf Reuther (ENAS)

<p>NANORIGO</p> <p>Special Scientific Coordination Meeting 2-3 February 2023 Burg Windeck, GERMANY</p> <p><small>This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant agreement 101019720.</small></p>	<p>NANORIGO</p> <p>Session 2: Open discussion of critical issues and questions (response to the questionnaire)</p> <p>Q1: What is RG?</p> <p>RG = complex process > technical RA; inclusion of concern assessment not self-evident; difference between theory and practice; precautionary principle needed; in practice defined by authorities: should be shaped to be able to implement RG; RG = RA + CA? RG balancing risks and concerns and accepting risks for the sake of the benefits; RG addresses also unknowns + uncertainties beyond risk; how CA addressed by commercial endusers?</p> <p><small>This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant agreement 101019720.</small></p>	<p>NANORIGO</p> <p>Q2: RG is a scientific or political process?</p> <p>RG = much a political process includes groups with different interests and background; needs early societal inclusion; scientific experts may act as advisors; RG = place where both political and scientific meet; RG is a mix of both; final evaluation and MGT decisions are political; scientific outcome only effective if politically acceptable; RG = process of weighing scientific insights and societal considerations; political as it addresses more than technical risks; political also in terms of "what stakeholders are included, and there relative importance?"</p> <p><small>This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant agreement 101019720.</small></p>
1	2	3
<p>NANORIGO</p> <p>Q3: Difference between nano RGF and chemicals RGF? Not much difference; but NM more complex: pre-assessment may be even more important; RGF needs to include unique nano-specifics; should not be separate; nano RGF could complement chemicals RGF; more stakeholder included in nano RG? Risks more uncertain and ambiguous; NR lessons learned: call attention for broader considerations; needs to consider future smart materials and emerging technologies</p> <p><small>This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant agreement 101019720.</small></p>	<p>NANORIGO</p> <p>Q4: Do we need a nano (or smart materials) specific of more general RGF</p> <p>Special nano RGF needed because of specific properties and greater complexity; especially for smart materials; extended general RGF may be sufficient; not sure if special NRGF needed; nano behaves different than bulk materials: not captured by general RA; specific NRGF because risks may change;</p> <p><small>This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant agreement 101019720.</small></p>	<p>NANORIGO</p> <p>Q5: Should topics that need a full governance approach be prioritised? And what topics and stakeholders should be involved?</p> <p>Prioritization of topics and stakeholders needed; which stakeholder are representative and affected? Prioritization of stakeholder may reduce usefulness of RG approach; should come out of the pre-assessment; uncertainty and complexity = good indicators for prioritization; important question: who are the most vulnerable groups?, the political process steers selection: things become an issue because someone makes it an issue; could be the task of a council or House: different stakeholder groups prioritise topics based on previous knowledge and gaps; risk management always embedded in a wider governance structure</p> <p><small>This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant agreement 101019720.</small></p>
4	5	6

<p>NANORIGO</p> <p>Q6: What stakeholders responsible to initiate RG? Each particular stakeholder; product developer? Without legal mandate, no RG process initiated; society gives mandate to regulation who can initiate; responsible innovation would start in the design phase; REACH: manufacturer initiate such a RG process together with regulators, CSO; all stakeholder involved to ensure a balanced RG process; responsibilities already legally fixed; RG can be taken up by relevant actors (EU, EFSA, ECHA etc.); NANORIGO suggested bringing also others onboard, e.g., CSO; independent body needed to invite other actors relevant to the topic;</p> <p> This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant agreement 101019150.</p>		
7	8	9
<p>NANORIGO</p> <p>Q9: How could we have better clarified the difficulties/complexities of an inclusive RG process? Took time to understand what RG really means; value for non-experts is the proposal of a well-organized/structured and reusable governance process in which different perspectives from different non-experts/multidisciplinary stakeholders are properly reflected; we were too generic? How to organize RG got too little attention, better use of CS would have helped? The more specific approaches elaborated ("how"), the more likely they will be implemented in a regulatory context; better to have worked closer to actual RG structures and processes, to identify a more practical way what is missing or needs improvement; We failed to address many questions that would have made this project more relevant and concrete (as was in the rubber tyre CS); too much focus on scientific/technical elements</p> <p> This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant agreement 101019150.</p>		
10	11	12

Q12: Main lessons learnt?

RG desirable but complex and laborious, PM could have helped; **RG > RA**, provide **a portal for all user groups difficult**; **KaRL = highlight!** impact of stakeholder guidance and strategic involvement in decision making; **open inclusive RG = complex, many conflicting interests**, responsible behavior towards people and environment; include opponents argument and agree on a final decision; coordination of large consortia requires specific skills; **pay attention to latest policies**; **mandatory NMBP-13 cooperation made the work not easier**: took a lot of time and resources not foreseen; **internal communication strategy was missing?** take **considerations from all stakeholders into account proves difficult to implement**, benefits from a RG hardly to make visible, **weighing of risks-concerns easier said than done**, **transdisciplinary discussions not easy to translate**, changes in practice of RG **rely on commitment of key players** (the Commission, ECHA, EFSA, etc), for which no overhaul of RG is really needed; **many hindering things came together**: NMBP-13 collaboration, pandemic (less direct stakeholder interaction) and nanotechnology appeared less important

This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement 821085.

Q13: 3 additional topics or statements for further discussion

- ✦ **How to maintain the web-based platform?**
- ✦ **How to make RGF sustainable?**
- ✦ **What strategic RG publications come from the project**
- ✦ **Publication policy**: why we need this special 'nano' RG framework?
- ✦ **Could our outcomes serve as input for other/new projects/proposals?**
- ✦ **How to use synergies of partners' capacities** in exploiting the achieved experience and forward it to customers (SSbD applicants) as effectively as possible?
- ✦ **How to assure that our relevant NRG output is used in a way that responsible actors 'can't do without it'?**
- ✦ **Communications and dissemination of the project - Stakeholder involvement?**
- ✦ **What is everyone's experience with the UC**: has it been helpful and how to improve this model for developing products that are useful for future users?

This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement 821085.

Appendix 6. Feedback from the OECD Event, Paris - Mark Morrison (OPTIMAT)

**Feedback from OECD Event
Paris
24-25/01/2023**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant agreement 851800.

Highlights

- Over 110 participants
- Each RT had >50 participants
- ~50% of participants were researchers
- Few NGOs
- But, key industry (e.g., BASF, EVONIK), policy (various DGs and some MS agencies) and other initiatives (e.g., PARC, AMI2030, VAMAS) all present
- Presentation by Jurgen Tiedje (Head Unit E3 Industrial Transformation, DG RTD)
 - Focus for EC is Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness
 - Green Deal, SSbD and digitalisation all critical
 - Stressed 'nano' no longer treated alone
 - Continuum of chemicals to materials encompassing ENMs
 - AMI2030 is most important link for NMBP-13 projects:
 - Vision: more collaboration
 - Safeguarding Europe's technology leadership
 - Reducing the environmental footprint
 - Securing Europe's strategic autonomy
- Ensuring EU 'sovereignty'

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant agreement 851800.

Harmonisation & Standardisation Roundtable

- Platform for H&S needed for coordination, dialogue and continuity (continuation of Malta Initiative)
- OECD strongly supportive -> TGs
- Needs a formal organisation to engage regulators
- Needs roadmap to deliver platform that involves all key stakeholders
- Needs to demonstrate an RoI
- Complements the chemicals activities of PARC
- Platform needs to be in place by Q1 2024

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant agreement 851800.

Are you in support of a European Test Methods Strategy that facilitates cooperation and support for the development of OECD Test Guidelines?

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant agreement 851800.

Portal & Tools Roundtable

- Initially will be supported by partners and hosted by NovaMechanics – future beyond initial 5 years is unclear
- Overall – appears too technical & not user-friendly
- Question – who is it for?
- Needs to provide filters and guidance to users to select optimal tools and explain any limitations
- Participants interested in and willing to support
- But ... not willing to pay (in the main)
- Different business models discussed from freemium, to paid services to ongoing funding via EU projects – could be used as dissemination vehicle

<https://nanoriskgov.eu>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant agreement 851800.

What would be the most important driver for you to use the portal?

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Rank	Driver
1st	Clarity of standards, guidelines, and guidance documents
2nd	Clarity of available tools
3rd	Clarity of different initiatives
4th	Regulatory overview
5th	Guidance on risk assessment

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant agreement 851800.

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FAIR Data Roundtable

- Removing remaining obstacles to FAIR data:
 - Citation standards – ensuring data is of certain quality, being clear where it may be lacking, common ontologies
 - Licensing – explain conditions of re-use
 - Training – on making data FAIR (e.g. eNanoMapper)
 - Use data papers to explain data interpretation not databases
 - Availability of resources – make use of existing initiatives, e.g. GoFAIR

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant agreement 823326.

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What do risk assessors need to increase data re-use?

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Risk Governance (House) Roundtable

- Identified gaps that 'House' could address
 - Guardian of risk based science/regulation
 - Need for adjudication mechanisms (to be developed)
 - Support in transition from nano to advanced materials
 - Stakeholders require a clear roadmap for SSbD,
 - Clear synergy with AMI2030
- Support for a House, and favoured more than roundtable, but a phased approach
- Needs more focus – demonstrate what it can do
- Question of whether the outputs would be binding/non binding
- Funding? Most believed it would need core, public funding, but predicated on industry 'need'
- AMI2030 will be critical to this

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- With regards to advanced nano materials, there could be serious issues of sustainability, which will be extremely difficult to assess and manage. The challenges at stake must be discussed openly, informed by the latest evidence as well as understanding of uncertainty and ambiguity, and follow formal processes.
- Such an open discussion could happen in the type of "House" proposed today, which could be able to meet expectations and needs from various stakeholders.
- The contribution of multidisciplinary expertise and participation of multiple stakeholder groups will ensure validity, legitimacy and acceptability of outcomes and informed recommendations developed by the House.
- Implementation of the House will require intellectual and financial resources, in proportion to expected outcomes and capacity of participating members.

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Next Steps

- Policy memorandum
- Engagement with the other initiatives
- Stronger likelihood for H&S and data > portal >> House?

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Appendix 7. What we have achieved in NANORIGO in the last four years (based on the deliverables achieved) - Rudolf Reuther (ENAS)

<p style="font-size: 8px;">This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant agreement 854888.</p>		
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<p style="font-size: 8px;">This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant agreement 854888.</p>		
4	5	6

<p>NANORIGO</p> <p>Session 1: What we have achieved in NANORIGO in the last four years?</p> <p>WP5: Case Studies Intermediate report on all CS (D5.1) Report: Case study on training (D5.2) Report: Case study on setting up a workplace (D5.3) Report: Case study on risk management (D5.4) Report: Case study on impact of RGF in Dutch industries (D5.5) Report: Case study on carbon nanofiber (D5.6) Report: Case Study on TiO2 (D5.7) Multimedia presentation on results of case studies (D5.8) Position on economic benefits from implementation of the RGF based on CS (D5.9)</p> <p> This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement 831035.</p> <p>9</p>		
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Appendix 8. Additional statements – Pieter van Broekhuizen (BKLb)

Session 2
Additional Statements

- It is an illusion to think that nano risk governance is nano specific
- The tasks requested from NMBP13 for the development of NRG are only window dressing to make further (environmentally unacceptable) economic growth acceptable

Appendix 9. D1.9 Stakeholder needs and interests - Daan Schuurbijs (DPF)

<p style="text-align: center;"> D1.9 - Stakeholder needs and interests Daan Schuurbijs, DPF NANORIGO Special Scientific Coordination Meeting, 2 Feb 2023 <small>This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement of 814530. This document reflects only the author's viewpoint. The Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.</small> </p>	<p>Chapter 2</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Your thoughts on the description of project activities? 2. Additions to specific paragraphs? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Marie-Valentine / Christina / Ludger / Mark: More specific needs identified in stakeholder events? 2. Pieter / Kees: More specific needs identified in UC? 3. Albert / Martin / Sabine / Norbert: Other findings from case studies? 4. Dana: Connect stakeholder needs analysis from risk communication platform blueprint? 5. Other items? 	<p>Chapter 3</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Agree with main points? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Stakeholders emerge in the context of the governance issues at hand; cannot be defined in advance (so an Organisational Form should not have fixed stakeholder representatives) 2. Stakeholders needs are diverse and should be identified on a case-by-case basis 3. Shared needs that emerged from NANORIGO: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Better grasp on nanotechnology governance landscape (not just distal) 2. Improve access to information 3. Collective sense-making: identifying problem scope and solution space 2. Can/should we say more? 	<p>Next steps</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deadline 15 Feb - your input by 12 Feb • Contributions from partners? • Use D1.9 and D4.10 for paper / policy brief?
<p>Statements (I)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The main stakeholder needs identified in NANORIGO were <i>not</i> related to data, but to the exchange of knowledge and experiences between stakeholders. • The main challenge in risk governance is to get stakeholders to talk to each other - and <i>listen</i>. • NMBP-13 does not practice what it preaches: the priorities identified for the Organisational Form have not been translated into any of the concrete project recommendations. • CSS and SSbD-policies pay lip service to stakeholder engagement but fail to realise it - and are thus doomed to fail 	<p>Statements (II)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NANORIGO was a 'mission impossible': it was asked to setup an organisation that none of the 'enactors' (policy makers in EU and industry) actually wanted. • Nano is not a hot topic for citizens; therefore 'bottom-up' stakeholder and citizen engagement won't work. • Risk governance is toothless if it doesn't involve 'hard decisions': blocking / prohibiting harmful applications / products. • As far as improved governance of nanomaterials are concerned, EU projects are counterproductive: they are an excuse for policy makers to take hard decisions on nanomaterials. 	<p>Statements (III)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the overall conceptual framework is focused solely on growth and competitiveness, it is impossible to realise a more encompassing view of risk governance (seriously considering the downsides of innovation as well as the expected benefits) • Forget 'sustainable growth' - the only way to survive as a species is by drastically reducing both production and consumption. 	

Appendix 10. Blueprint: How to build a risk communication platform to support NRG - Dana Kühnel (UFZ)

<p>NANORIGO Nanotechnology Risk Governance Framework</p> <p>NANORIGO Risk Governance aims to develop and implement a transparent, transdisciplinary Nanotechnology Risk Governance Framework and a related Risk Governance Council</p> <p>Start</p> <p>Special Scientific Coordination Meeting Burg Windeck, 2.-3.2.2023</p> <p>The project is funded by the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Actions</p>	<p>Task description</p> <p>T3.5 Development of a clear risk communication platform into the RGF including all stake- holders (M1-46) Participants: UFZ (Leader), AU, UAVR, UBREMEN, BOKU, TGO, DPF, DECHEMA, FIOH</p> <p>Approaches to support a proper and transparent risk communication and transfer of safety information, e.g. safety data sheets and exposure scenarios based on regulations, will be developed. All partners involved have previously set up similar communication systems for producers and users of NM, where the user has been able to interact, e.g., in defining the exposure situation, to promote a proper assessment of the uses in the supply chain. Experience gained in communicating safety aspects of NM and in collaborating on a knowledgebase of NM (www.nanoobjects.info) will be used to support risk communication tailored for different stakeholder groups. As an example, descriptions will be elaborated for the project website to describe NANORIGO findings and news in a tiered manner, starting with a relative simple wording (for laypersons) based on the risk management tool developed in T2.4. The complexity of the presentation will gradually increase when the description goes further, and the last part will finally provide information for scientists. A systematic communication methodology, able to indicate when scientific information is either incomplete or contested, will be included. Results will be presented in deliverable D3.2 The Risk Governance Framework proto-type (M27) and D3.3 Science-based transdisciplinary Risk Governance Framework for NM (M46).</p>
<p>Blueprint „How to build a risk communication platform to support nano risk governance“</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Summary of approach and work done • Proposal for structure of future RC platform • Proposal for multidisciplinary expert involvement 	
<p>3</p>	<p>4</p>

Blueprint: How to build a risk communication platform to support nano risk governance

With contributions by Bernd Giese, Daan Schuurbiers, Nils Bohmer, Maud Bohmert, Martin Mullins, Irini Fuxzhi, Mark Morrison...

Compiled by Andreas Mattern, Dana Kühnel,

Platform: Arantxa, Francisco Huertas, Blanca Pozuelo Rollón

Figure 1: Graphical abstract – The three elements of the NanoRigo risk communication platform. “Knowledge”: background information on nanosafety and risk governance. “Analysis”: several tools for exposure, hazard and risk assessment for nanomaterials. “Exchange”: forum for discussion and dialog among experts and stakeholders on nanosafety issues.

Introduction

The NanoRigo Risk Communication (RC) platform aims to support an understandable and transparent risk communication and provide clear nanosafety information to all potential stakeholders at risk or concerned about nano-specific risks. It is integrated in the NanoRigo Risk Governance Platform.

According to the definition by WHO the risk communication refers to the exchange of real-time information, advice and opinions between experts and people facing threats to their health, economic or social well-being (<https://www.who.int/emergencies/risk-communications>).

Depending on the three types of risk (Care, Consensus and Crisis) different plans of actions have to be considered [1]. In case of a crisis (e.g. a disease outbreak) immediate information about the crisis, preventable and protectable measurements and an instant reaction of authorities is a key for a good risk communication. For a risk which is long known (Care) safety rules must be provided while the

Consensus risk communication focus on involving the people at risk to find a solution. This is often the case in safety planning for risk which cannot be excluded (e.g. building of a nuclear power plant). The ultimate purpose of risk communication is to enable people at risk to take informed decisions to protect themselves and their loved ones.

Risk communication uses many communications techniques ranging from media and social media communications, mass communications and community engagement. It requires a sound understanding of people’s perceptions, concerns, and beliefs as well as their knowledge and practices. It also requires the early identification and management of rumours, misinformation, and other challenges.

Emerging technologies, or specific technologies in general (e.g. green genetic engineering) often lead to safety concerns among stakeholders, touching fields like consumer, occupational or environmental health. The more difficult a potential danger or risk is to grasp, the more essential is a good risk communication. This is particularly important when the potential hazard may affect many sections of the population. In the case of nanotechnology, potential concerns arise mainly from the small size of nanomaterials, enabling them theoretically to pass body barriers such as skin or air-blood barrier. In addition, the chemical composition (e.g. copper) as well as specific physical-chemical properties (e.g. surface functionalisations) raise(d) for adverse effects in humans as well as environmental organisms. It is important to address all concerns in an understanding and tolerant way, taking them seriously.

To implement this approach, the NanoRigo project was initiated, to deal with potential concerns on nanomaterials in the society. This includes the involvement of different stakeholder groups, the consideration of concerns from different population groups, and the participation of all these groups in the risk assessment process of nanomaterials. To address all these challenges, the project developed a Nano Risk Governance Framework (RGF). The RGF is represented by the online NanoRigo Risk Governance Platform. To enable the stakeholders to better understand nanotechnology-related risks and deal with concerns, the NanoRigo Risk Communication (RC) platform was integrated. The RC platform aims at providing general information on nanomaterials as well as the risk governance process, but also specific help in assessing nanomaterials risks by using specific tools as well as the proper communication of the results obtained. This is in line with Isigonis et al (2019) [2], who suggest specifically for the case of communicating nanomaterials risks that risk communication should explain the results a given risk assessment tool provides to all users verbally and/or visually and justify resulting recommendations for actions. It should also communicate the magnitude of associated uncertainty of the knowledge.

Approach to develop a risk communication platform on nanomaterial safety.

STEP 1 – Stakeholder survey

First, a group of experts from the NanoRigo team created a stakeholder list. A stakeholder is a person or group that has a legitimate interest in the course or outcome of a process or project. In the frame of the NanoRigo project, the stakeholders considered are listed in the ANNEX in Table 1. It is all groups potentially interested in risks of nanomaterials. For each of the groups, envisaged needs and knowledge gaps in relation to nanosafety were then listed according to expert knowledge (See Table in – ANNEX) [3]. Primarily, the idea was to provide stakeholder-specific risk communication. However, from this stakeholder interest survey exercise, we concluded that it will be quite ambitious to reach all these groups through one platform, since they all have different interests and need to be reached in different ways. Communicating in a targeted manner will require much effort not only for communication as such, but specifically for the exploration of specific interests and the subsequent selection of the respective communication tools. E.g. for participatory formats, to what extent stakeholders would be willing and able to join in, and under what conditions. If stakeholder specific communication is taken seriously, it will require significant resources from experts.

A good tool is to create a Risk communication plan. A risk communication plan aims at summarizing the goals, participants, main messages, and methods used for risk communication on a specific issue of concern. A good way is proposed in the form of a Risk communication toolkit (<https://rc-1.itrcweb.org/appendix-a-risk-communication-plan-description-and-template/>), which provides templates for the parts of a communication plan. It is adaptable to nanosafety related risk issues. [1]

At this stage, the nano-specific concerns of stakeholders were unknown, but we realised that quite an amount of background information from external resources is available already. This led to the second step in the establishment of the NanoRigo risk communication platform. In addition, a potential knowledge gap for most stakeholders was identified, namely knowledge on the risk governance process. This led to the third step, the development of guidance through the risk governance process.

STEP 2 – Review of existing communication efforts

A review of existing nanosafety communication initiatives was conducted, with the aim to avoid duplications and link to existing knowledge and information. The focus of our risk communication activities shall be on specific knowledge and information gaps to provide unique information for the stakeholders / users. Certain criteria for the selection of external information sources were applied: information and knowledge shall not be outdated, should comply with the framework conditions of the NanoRigo RGF, and transparency about funding. The external information sources were then integrated into RGF platform as described later (Figure 8).

STEP 3 – Development of guidance on the risk governance process

As most stakeholders may not be familiar with the risk governance process, one aim is to provide stakeholders / users of the RGF platform with specific information on the risk governance process as

such. This is done by providing background information, explanations on the results of the RGF process. The risk governance process consists of 6 steps of assessment, in addition to nanomaterial specific assessment tools. The guidance on the tools is developed by Task 2.1 and provided by the platform webpage and its structure. Hence, it is not further elaborated here. However, for the description of tools, some graphical elements were developed, in order to avoid lengthy textual explanations.

Establishment / integration of the Risk communication platform into the RGF platform

Based on the outcome of our survey on stakeholders needs, the requirements and structure for the NANORIGO risk communication platform were constructed. It consists of three pillars, as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The first pillar corresponds to the knowledge part of the risk communication platform and provides background information on nano risk governance. This can be implemented within the web-based platform. The second pillar represents the exchange part, which will require direct interaction between stakeholders and experts. This can be done either via online communication tools, or via physical meetings. The last pillar is also part of the knowledge section and provides information on nanosafety from external sources.

In principle, this implies that part of the risk communication activities can be done on a virtual platform in a static way, whereas also physical interaction between experts and stakeholders is required that may also be done in the virtual space (forum, video conferences), but requires more attention and effort (i.e., presence of an expert). It was decided to integrate the virtual risk communication platform into the web-based NanoRigo Risk governance platform. In the following, the implementation of each pillar into the platform is demonstrated.

Finally, for each part of the communication activities the most important functions are listed, to estimate the effort and required personnel and facilitate the full implementation of the risk communication platform in the future.

Pillar 1) The aim is to make stakeholders familiar with risk governance, by providing guidance through the risk governance process and the platform by several means. Additional orientation is provided by pictograms and explanations for the tools implemented in the platform. This pillar provides information on the risk governance process as such, as most stakeholders may not be familiar with risk governance. The aim is to prepare users for the RG process. This part of the RC platform is planned to be static on the webpage e.g., provide guidance on the results obtained by individual tools in the RGF (beyond the RC information already provided by the tools, Isigonis et al. may provide input). The effort need for maintenance is low but content needs updates from time to time.

1.1 Potential Implementation

Figure 3+4 Screenshots from RGF platform: Figure 3 shows the landing page. Figure 4 shows the different parts of the platform.

Figure 5: Platform guidelines gives an overview about the involved researchers and experts and their role in the NRGF.

Figure 4: Next to a short video about the basic functions of the platform, different stakeholders and researcher who are involved in the NANORIGO project are quoted and act as testimonials. Thereby the audience become familiar with the platform.

Figure 5: The "general information" part provides detailed as well as short information about what to expect from the platform, what kind of information can be found and how to use the platform.

Figure 8: For the analysis part which contains the selection of risk assessment tools, an easy-to-understand explanation part with pictures and only a few sentences is needed for quick user guidance. Thereby future users and stakeholders who are not familiar with the risk assessment steps understand each selection step.

Pillar 2) Outreach of nanosafety information: This pillar provides stakeholders additional information sources on [nanosafety](#) and it is based on a survey on valuable platforms providing background information on nanosafety. The platforms selected according to the criteria mentioned above (see Figure 8) are briefly described on the platform, and links are provided. The aim is to provide stakeholders information on nanosafety/risk communication activities beyond NANORIGO RGF. The content of this outreach pillar needs to be checked and updated from time to time but the effort needed for maintenance is considered to be low.

Figure 6: The "Outreach" part shows an overview about existing data- and knowledge platforms related to nanotechnology and nanosafety. By selecting a checkbox, only the relevant databases are shown while the others are greyed out.

Pillar 3) Convey risk governance outcomes. Depending on the issue of concern, involvement of different stakeholder groups and the methods and tools used to tackle a nanosafety issue, the results and outcomes of the risk governance process will be conveyed in different ways. But for a risk governance process is finished, interactions between stakeholders and experts /risk governors are required.

1 Advice and explanations during the RG process:

On the platform this can be provided by implementing an 'ask the expert' option to allow direct interaction between stakeholders/users and experts on outcomes of RG procedures. But most communication might need direct exchange between experts and stakeholders to discuss the results obtained by running multiple tools. Practical help with data retrieval and running the tools might be needed. The results of a risk governance process have to be brought together in a concise way. The related uncertainties and consequences need to be explored in order to find risk management options.

Direct communication (in the virtual space or physically) requires various skills, for example scientific expertise on data evaluation (e.g. by applying the [K&S&L](#) system) or use of the tools, but also risk governors and communication specialists (see below for more elaboration). Overall, this communication option requires persons bringing profound expertise which can devote time to this task.

2. Communication between stakeholders / users:

Here virtual tools for two-way communication or a forum for open communication among stakeholders can be implemented into the RC platform. This communication option option needs moderation and therefore requires some expert involvement.

So far, data retrieval, evaluation and reuse are not considered in the risk communication platform. The KaRL system has been developed by NanoRigo partners, but has so far not been implemented within the RG platform. As data form the basis for the usage of many of the tools implemented in the RG platform, advice on data retrieval may need to be considered for RC as well, especially, as the amount, quality and fit-for-purpose of available data are essential to determine uncertainty and define data and knowledge gaps (-> risk management).

This pillar will require most efforts and expertise to be operationalised. It needs constant attention by experts / risk governors. Since the realisation format of the Council/House/Structure and thereby the resources available for these kinds of services are unclear, it was decided that this functionality of the NANORIGO RC blueprint is left out from the current realisation of the RC platform, but essential functionalities are discussed.

Figure 7: The exchange part is intended to be implemented by having an "Ask the expert" button which could lead to an email exchange or a live chat. Another idea would be a general chat where users, admins and occasionally experts are talking to each other.

NanoRigo case studies

Additional inspiration on risk communication of nanomaterials could be deduced from the case studies. Short video clips extracted from the videos produced by the University of Salzburg may be used to explain the platform, e.g. by using interviews for testimonials. However, most of the case studies conducted did not use the RG platform and tools, so that limited input is expected from that side.

The closest collaboration took place with the rubber tyres case study, dealing with the potential impact of nanomaterials used in the production of rubber. The study elaborated the concern that tyre rubber particles released by abrasion will lead to a release of nanomaterials, with potential

negative impacts on human health and the environment. This hypothetical case was elaborated under participation of stakeholders from industry and society (e.g. tyres, manufactures, citizens, employers and trade unions), by conducting a risk governance process (without using the RGF platform, which was not operational at that time). An extensive data collection and evaluation formed the basis. On a workshop with the stakeholders, the ideas on the design of the risk communication were presented. [3] As the RGF was not used during the case study, there was no further input from the stakeholders with regard to the risk communication platform.

Any input from the user committee?

Future resources

As elaborated, the process of risk communication in the frame of nano risk governance and setting up a related risk communication platform requires involvement of various experts, to fully cover the needs of users / stakeholders during the risk governance process. In the frame of the NanoRigo project, during the course of the project the full design of the risk communication platform with regard to responsibilities (council? House?), resources (person- as well as money wise), and expert involvement in the future could not be elaborated. The RGF platform and the integrated RC platform are not yet fully operationalised.

What functions / persons / effort is needed to fulfil all the functions of a risk communication platform as outlined above?

The interaction between stakeholders/users and experts / risk governors needs resources as well as relevant knowledge (on risk governance, risk assessment, the tools, data handling...). For the future establishment of a risk communication platform, here the basic functions are summarized in the Table below.

Role	Task/Function
Expert Risk assessment	Knowledge in risk assessment specific for nanomaterials (Environment, Occupational, Human)
Expert on the Tools	Provide help with tools, assist with data input and interpretation of output, help stakeholders to combine the results from several tools
Expert Data	Support stakeholders in data retrieval, <u>assessment</u> of data quality and data gaps
Risk governor	Support stakeholders in the risk governance process
Moderator – virtual space	Check <u>stakeholders</u> comments in the forum, support
Moderator / communicator– physical	Moderate stakeholder discussions online or during physical meetings, e.g. round tables, conflicts among stakeholders
Social scientist	Social ethical aspects
Risk communicator	Support stakeholders in finding the communication strategy for their specific nano-issue or e.g. for disastrous events [4, 5]
Science communication	Provide stakeholders with nanosafety information and explain
Advisory board or council	discuss complex issues and provide input
Content manager webpage	For maintenance of web-based platform, updating content
IT / <u>Webdesigner</u>	Restructuring web platform

Further issues to consider

Ownership / Responsibility / copyright for platform webpage

Data protection issues

Figure 9: Role of risk communication within the RG process.

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ANNEX

Table 1 Assessment of stakeholders having an interest in nano risk communication and their specific needs [5].

Stakeholder group	Interest in which risks-related issues?	Knowledge needs related to nanotechnology
Governmental agencies	Governmental agencies due to their rather "systemic" view and responsibility for anticipatory governance (in the EU in accordance with the precautionary principle) are interested in characteristics and circumstances that may impair their ability to foresee, classify and manage risks. In terms of their systemic responsibility authorities are interested in avoiding vulnerabilities. Therefore all effects that may have an impact on the a) exposure, b) sensitivity and c) adaptive capacity of the society are of relevance. All three aspects constitute the vulnerability of a society and nowadays increasingly find their expression in the regulation of „risk technologies“ as genetic engineering, synthetic chemistry etc. Thus, there are goals for achieving a) the protection of specific elements of the socio-economic and ecological system (protection goals), b) assure control and safety of the applied technologies and its products and c) limit the spread of potentially harmful substances/entities.	In particular, for new and emerging technologies state authorities are interested in 1. indications for gaps in regulation due to the specific character of the technology or composition of the products/material which does not fall under the scope of current regulation (e.g. if REACH definitions turn out as inappropriate), 2. new hazard and exposure pathways, 3. early indicators for hazard and exposure 4. lack of information which is necessary for hazard and exposure analysis (e.g. physico-chemical properties, toxicological information etc.) 5. whether the current tools for hazard and risk assessment are applicable 6. potential environmental impact in terms of emissions, resource consumption or the capability for a circular economy.
Researchers / academia	Nanotechnology is multi-disciplinary in character. Hence, researchers from many disciplines are involved and interested in a broad range of topics with regard to their risks. In general, the interests concern novel developments and achievement of understanding of basics and phenomena. There is not always a clear relation to risk assessment.	1. Appropriateness and novelty in methodology (PC characterisation, analytics, toxicity assays) 2. Novel developments in particle generation and applications 3. Physical properties of nanomaterials, synthesis 4. Mechanistic understanding of nanomaterial hazard, dose-response relationships.... 5. Workplace safety / safe handling / labelling / safe disposal of nanomaterials in the laboratory context (GHS, CPL)

Standardisation bodies	Are interested less in specific risks, but in standardisation needs arising from nanotechnology and nanosafety, which may be related to risk and hazard assessment (e.g. development of appropriate standards for toxicity testing).	They need information from both research and industry, and representatives from both for the respective boards and committees, hence for them also the networking aspect comes into play (identification of relevant stakeholders in various fields)
Civil society organisations, NGOs	Different types of CSOs have different interests and 'knowledge needs'. Environmental organisations are interested in environmental impacts of nanomaterials; consumer organisations are interested in health impacts of consumer products; trade unions are interested in impacts of nanomaterials in the workplace. Each 'type' of CSO could benefit from an overview of websites and organisations that provide reliable information. The KIR-Nano website of the RIVM in the Netherlands for instance publishes newsletters on present and future developments regarding the risks of nanotechnology. E.g. the European NANOCAP project aimed to empower environmental NGOs and Trade Unions to participate in the debate on nanotechnologies. They called for [3]: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transparency and openness regarding processes and products that contain nanomaterials; - Development of specific tools for nanomaterial use that put the precautionary principle in practice; - Reporting of the type and content of nanoparticles - Register of workers possibly exposed to nanoparticles, - The use of nano reference values as guides to assess workplace exposure to nanoparticles 	Ideally, they should be targeted individually. Their knowledge needs are highly specific: i.e. CSOs are interested in information - and opportunities for participation - that address the specific interest that they represent (because of limited resources, CSOs usually have to make hard decisions on what they decide to become involved in). CSOs are not just looking for access to information; they are also looking for ways to become involved in debates (see also this press release: Civil society demands action, not words, on nanotechnology) from the Government for International Environmental Law (GIEL), an environmental NGO).
Networks / associations / Non-profit organisations / Think tanks	Depending on their field of activity, they are interested in specific content for their stakeholder group(s) (members, partners).	Available funding, cooperation opportunities, scientific progress, new products: associated risks and new regulations, opinions/concerns of other stakeholders
Insurances	In terms of exposure management, insurers and reinsurers would be interested in understanding the life cycle of NMs . The life cycle implies for insurers	Insurance professionals will have different needs depending on the function within the insurance market. Underwriters will require a

	<p>exposure across different "lines of business" included employers liability, product liability/recall and environmental risk.</p> <p>As the ultimate unit of analysis is monetary, scale and economy are important considerations for insurers. Work currently taking place in RISKGONE will assist in this regard.</p>	<p>relatively non-granular approach in terms of the risk communicated. A "tool" that allows them to quickly identify areas of concern would be attractive. This could take a control banding or traffic light form and would allow underwriters to refer more difficult cases to a risk engineering function.</p> <p>Risk Manager and risk engineers would require more granular information. This could include decision trees and be populated with data on specific processes which would allow the risk management function to engage with clients on risk mitigation measures. Risk communication tools that would help this group map out mitigation strategies would be particularly useful. The ability to quantify the impact of mitigation would be attractive.</p>		<p>Trade Union Institute (ETUI) for the NanoDiode project. EU-OSHA website on Managing Materials in the Workplace, or FIOH</p>		<p>currently inviting citizens to become involved in nanotechnologies.</p>
Interested citizens, consumers, end users				<p>European citizens are cautiously optimistic about nanotechnologies: they have positive expectations, but they also have concerns about the risks to human and environmental health and to societal well-being in general. Innovations addressing the great societal challenges of our time like environmental and energy applications are viewed positively, but consumers are more sceptical about applications in food, cosmetics and cleaning products – especially if the product does not have obvious benefits compared to 'traditional' products. Therefore, the NANORIGO risk communication platform could:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Make clear and compelling, up-to-date information about the risks and benefits of nanotechnology available to citizens. Many websites with information on nanotechnologies for the general public (like Nano & Me) date back to the early stages of the nanotechnology hype (2005 - 2010). Much of this is now outdated. 2. Empower citizens to become involved in the debate on nanotechnologies. The GoNano project recently reviewed existing opportunities for citizens and professional stakeholders to engage with nanotechnologies. One of the conclusions was that more engagement initiatives are needed that focus on the 'empowerment' of citizens and stakeholders rather than on educating, informing or inspiring citizens or stakeholders. GoNano also developed a 'Join the nanodebate' section on its website. This page briefly explains what nanotechnology is and why being part of the nanodebate might be interesting for citizens, using supporting resources like inspiring videoclips, a 'how to...' guide about public participation, and more. One of the features of this website section is a public engagement database, listing organizations and projects that are 	<p>Citizens generally indicate that they feel poorly informed about the topic and welcome more consumer-oriented information. However, previous efforts to engage citizens with nanotechnologies show low levels of participation (for various reasons). See also:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Joubert et al (2020): Public perception and knowledge on nanotechnology. A study based on a citizen science approach. - NanoDiode citizen survey and in-depth interviews. - Eurobarometer report: Public opinion on future innovations, science and technology of June 2015. - Nanoview, a survey of 88 international studies on public perceptions of nanotechnologies published after 2000 <p>Citizens and end-users may be interested in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accessible, clear information about nanotechnology. The information should be easy to find and must be up-to-date; citizens are influenced by the media and search for topics and information that is currently relevant. Interest may increase when the information is linked to specific <i>applications</i> (rather than to science and technology in general), and the application is of <i>personal interest</i>. - Practical information on where to ask questions or how to engage in the nanotechnology debate. 	
Developers, producers	<p>They are interested in the potential hazards of new materials/technologies under development and their impact on risk management and regulation. But in the same way revaluations of already established products are one of the main interests.</p>	<p>They search for active involvement in working groups but also for guidance documents and consulting services.</p>				
Funding agencies	<p>Observation of research landscape and R&D in industry</p> <p>Funding into safety research implies the need to observe the development of potentially hazardous materials & chemicals</p>	<p>Identification of future research needs in the field, which may involve hazard and risk of novel materials</p> <p>Strategic assessment of knowledge gaps and support needs</p>				
Press / multipliers	<p>The media are interested in good stories – these can be about both risks and benefits of nanotechnologies, as long as it's newsworthy (defined by proximity, timeliness, interest and impact). A big health scare is a good story, but so is a new gadget that will change our daily lives.</p>	<p>'Risk governance' isn't very newsworthy in itself. In addition, the risk governance and risk communication platforms should take a neutral position between the different parties, and not overemphasize neither risks nor benefits of nanotechnology.</p>				
Workers in nanotechnology	<p>Workers need clear and accessible information on the use of nanomaterials in the workplace.</p> <p>This is already covered by several institutions (see for example these presentations about health and safety for workers developed by the European</p>	<p>How to determine if nanomaterials are present in the workplace? How to minimize exposure? Which personal protection to use?</p>				

Appendix 11. D3.4 Guidance document for RGF - Rudolf Reuther (ENAS) on behalf of Milja Koponen (TTL)

<p>Slide 3: Draft Executive Summary</p> <p>One of the main objectives of the NANORIGO-project is to develop and implement a transparent, transdisciplinary, and science-based Risk Governance Framework (RGF) for managing risks induced by manufactured nanomaterials and nano-enabled products while considering social, environmental, and economic aspects. The approach is based on identified high-quality data (WP1), advanced scientific tools (WP2, WP3) and risk communication with all stakeholders (WP3) and will align, integrate, and upgrade most advanced science-based approaches and knowledge to be used during the risk governance process. The nano risk governance framework developed in the NANORIGO project is based on the IRGC framework (IRGC 2007, Renn & Roco, 2006), which is adapted for the needs of the risk governance of nanomaterials. The framework is operationalized with a web-based platform which is planned to be integrated within the common NMBP-13 portal. This status report will summarise the efforts related to the Nanotechnology Risk Governance Framework and the associated web-platform in different NANORIGO WPs and reported in various NANORIGO deliverables and working documents.</p>		
<p>1</p>	<p>2</p>	<p>3</p>
<p>Slide 6: Starting points for discussion of D3.4</p> <p>What is the one finding in D3.4 that should be communicated to a wider audience, and how would you communicate this (in one sentence) in a policy brief or future research paper?</p> <p>Provide practical guidance for stakeholders along the risk governance process on how to use the risk governance framework operationalized by a user-friendly web-portal, to select and apply appropriate methods, tools, procedures and data sources required for different purposes to perform the RG process (e.g., to meet regulatory demands or design/develop a new product/technology or innovations).</p>		
<p>4</p>	<p>5</p>	<p>6</p>

<p>NANORIGO</p> <p>What else should be done to enhance the success of the deliverable and increase its visibility?</p> <p>Spread information that demonstrate the successful applicability of the risk governance framework by means of practical case studies performed in NANORIGO reflecting various types of risks and different industrial, regulatory and social situations, e.g., by means of factsheets available at the project website, the web-portal etc.)</p> <p> This project has received funding from The European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement 851896.</p> <p>9</p>		
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Appendix 12. Publication on economic benefits from implementing the RGF, based on case studies - Martin Mullins, (TGO)

Task 5.7 Economic benefits of the Risk Governance Framework

D5.9. Publication on economic benefits from implementing the RGF, based on case studies.

TGO

NANORIGO

TRANSZERO

1

NANORIGO
Risk Governance Framework

NANORIGO

Steps

Cross-cutting Functions

- Context Analysis
- Risk Communication
- Stakeholder Engagement
- Process Coordination

4) Monitoring and Reporting

1) Risk Identification
+ Per-incident

3) Risk Treatment
+ Solutions
+ Management

2) Risk Analysis
+ Technical Risk Assessment
+ Operational Context Assessment

Alignment of RGF to traditional Risk Management Cycle

1. Risk Identification
2. Risk Analysis
3. Risk Treatment
4. Risk Monitoring and Reporting

D5.9. Publication on economic benefits from implementing the RGF, based on case studies (TGO)

2

NANORIGO

Steps

Cross-cutting Functions

- Context Analysis
- Risk Communication
- Stakeholder Engagement
- Process Coordination

4) Monitoring and Reporting

1) Risk Identification
+ Per-incident

3) Risk Treatment
+ Solutions
+ Management

2) Risk Analysis
+ Technical Risk Assessment
+ Operational Context Assessment

Improved Risk Understanding

Economic Factors

- Health and Safety
- Risk Transfer and Insurance
- Environmental, Social and Governance
- Investment and Funding

D5.9. Publication on economic benefits from implementing the RGF, based on case studies (TGO)

3

Interrogating NANORIGO RGF from SII perspective

SOLVENCY II

- Pillar 1**
Financial Requirements
- Pillar 2**
Governance & Supervision
- Pillar 3**
Reporting & Disclosure

D5.9. Publication on economic benefits from implementing the RGF, based on case studies (TGO)

4

TRANSGERO

Wider ESG type Metrics

- PROVIDING EMPLOYMENT**
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.
- HEALTH IMPROVEMENT**
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- BIODIVERSITY PROTECTION**
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- REFORESTATION**
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.
- SOCIAL WELLBEING**
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[LEARN MORE](#)

DS.9. Publication on economic benefits from implementing the RGF, based on case studies (TGO)

5

Thank You.

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NANORIGO

TRANSGERO
OPENING NEW RESEARCH SOLUTIONS AND TRAINING

6

Appendix 13. Options for the form and funding of an NRG Organizational Form - Mark Morrison (OPTIMAT)

D7.5 - Options for the form and funding of a Nanotechnology Risk Governance Organisational Form

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement 825260.

Context for D7.5

- Originally the business plan for the Council
- But a discrete body no longer wanted by EC
- Amendment in 2022 – to review options for an entity that could support risk governance
- Extended remit to support Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS) and Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD)
- Needs to consider how it engages with other new initiatives, mainly PARC and AMI2030
- Needs to consider how the NRGOF could utilise other project results: RGF, data, tools and portal

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement 825260.

Options

- A roundtable (light – focuses on stakeholder discussions)
- A house (roundtable plus data, knowledge, tools, portal, RGF)
- No new organisation (assets are taken up by range of organisations or not)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement 825260.

Landscape that House would operate in

Organisation	Function
European Union Observatory for Nanomaterials (EUON)	Provides information about nanomaterials already on the EU market through existing public databases
High Level Roundtable on the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS HLR)	The mission of the expert group is to realise the objectives of the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability and to monitor its implementation in dialogue with the stakeholders concerned. Meets 2x p.a. on request of DG ENW. Members are selected based on their competence and experience.
European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC)	PARC aims to advance research, share knowledge and improve skills in chemical risk assessment. By doing so, it will help support the European Union's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, paving the way for the "zero pollution" ambition announced in the European Green Deal
Advanced Materials 2030 Initiative (AMI2030)	Vision is to deliver a strong European Materials ecosystem to drive the green and digital transition as well as a sustainable inclusive European society through a systemic collaboration of upstream developers, downstream users and citizens and all stakeholders in between. Has delivered a roadmap and in February 2023 will deliver a Strategic Research Agenda (SRA) for advanced materials.
Scientific Committee on Health, Environmental and Emerging Risks (SCHEER)	Provides opinions on questions concerning emerging or newly identified health and environmental risks and on broad, complex or multidisciplinary issues that require a comprehensive assessment of risks to consumer safety or public health and related issues not covered by other European Union risk assessment bodies. Members expected to attend at least 70% of all meetings.
Malta Initiative	To ensure that nano specific aspects of Test Guidelines and Guidance Documents are fulfilled for regulatory purposes.

... plus others operating in different spaces

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Results of Stakeholder Consultations (WP4 & WP7)

- Different stakeholder groups feel quite differently about the 'House'
 - Industry (less positive):
 - questioned need for new organisation – would use EUON (or ECHA, EMA, EFSA)
 - lack of clarity as to focus and remit
 - would output be 'binding'?
 - Policy & regulation (more positive):
 - trusted environment for in-depth, multistakeholder dialogue
 - address concerns in an informed & impartial manner
 - NGOs/CSOs – no strong engagement ('nano' not currently a high priority)
- Way forward?
 - Preference for house vs roundtable (OECD & online survey)
 - "permanent reference point" and a "problem solving capacity"
 - Phased approach – needs to demonstrate efficacy
 - Must be more than 'nano'- link to advanced materials – AMI2030 engagement a priority

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Operational Considerations for Different Options

OpCon	Option	Roundtable	House	No New Organization
Status		Ad hoc Independent	Permanent Independent	Dependent on host(s)
Staff		Secretariat	Secretariat Executive & research staff	Dictated by host(s)
Level of funding required		++	+++	n.a.
Funding requirements		Governing Board Members Expert participation in assessments	In addition to roundtable costs: Core staff/secretariat Possible longer-term secondments	As required by host(s)
Funding source		In-kind Public sector: Core funding Grants for specific activities	In addition to roundtable: Private and third sector funding Member fees	From host institution(s)
Additional income sources		Unclear	Fees for professional services, including access to experts, tools and data	Unclear

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NANORIGO Operational Considerations for Different Options

OpCon	Option	Roundtable	House	No New Organisation
Expert selection & engagement		Independent Experts register Multi-sector Multi-disciplinary Expert focus groups	Independent Experts register Multi-sector Multi-disciplinary Expert focus groups	Dictated by host(s)
Activities		Stakeholder engagement & networking Identifying issues Assessing emerging issues Formulating joint positions Developing plans to improve risk governance Public engagement	In addition to roundtable activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Broader stakeholder engagement Systematic use of data and tools (through the Framework and Portal) Maintaining the Framework and Portal (and thus tools and data) Monitoring the status of nano risk governance Longer-term projects (e.g., Framework Programme) 	Dictated by host(s)
Services		Expert multi-stakeholder and disciplinary opinion & recommendations	In addition to roundtable services: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In-depth analysis Consultancy Training 	Dictated by host(s)

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NANORIGO Operational Considerations for Different Options

OpCon	Option	Roundtable	House	No New Organisation
Mode of action		Responsive Flexible Agile Short to mid-term	Responsive Flexible Agile Longer-term	Dictated by host(s)
Governance		Independent Board Terms of reference	Independent Board Formal statutes	Dictated by host(s)
Breadth		Limited	Potentially larger, dependent on budget	Dictated by host(s)
Capacity		Limited	Potentially larger, dependent on budget	Dictated by host(s)
Accessibility		Publicly available output	Publicly available output Publicly available guidance, tools and data	Dictated by host(s) and/or funding source

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NANORIGO

PESTLE Analysis:

- **Political** – EC, MS and other organisations
- **Economic** – funding
- **Social** – representativeness
- **Technological** – managing data, tools and portal
- **Legal** – how are outputs perceived and used
- **Environmental** – maintaining pace

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NANORIGO POLITICAL

Factor	Resolution	Impact
EUON has a focus on ENMs		
EC considers nanomaterials as part of the chemicals /advanced materials spectrum		
OF needs to consider CSS & SSbD		
EC has supported a number of initiatives (PARC, AMI2030)		

Impact: H (high), M (medium), L (low)

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NANORIGO ECONOMIC

Factor	Resolution	Impact
No clear route for public funding		
Format of in-kind contributions		
Payment for services model		
Appetite of MS to support an OF		

Impact: H (high), M (medium), L (low)

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NANORIGO SOCIAL

Factor	Resolution	Impact
Ensuring broad stakeholder representation		
Addressing different concerns and priorities across different MS		
Addressing broader stakeholder concerns equitably		
Legitimacy of OF recommendations to different stakeholders		

Impact: H (high), M (medium), L (low)

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NANORIGO

TECHNOLOGICAL

Factor	Resolution	Impact
User needs not met by the portal		
Output requires specific expertise not available to OF		
Ongoing maintenance of the portal		
Licensing technology from others		

Impact: H (high), M (medium), L (low)

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NANORIGO

LEGAL

Factor	Resolution	Impact
Changing regulations		
Engagement with regulatory agencies		
New H&S TG		
Legal status of OF recommendations		

Impact: H (high), M (medium), L (low)

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ENVIRONMENTAL

Factor	Resolution	Impact
Missing data		
Robustness of tools		
Ability to update tools and data to keep pace with external developments		

Impact: H (high), M (medium), L (low)

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Appendix 14. Session 4 'On Second Thoughts' - Rudolf Reuther (ENAS)

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